

2-Mercaptobenzo- γ -Thiopyrone as an Analytical Reagent for Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II).

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2-mercaptobenzo γ -thiopyrone (MBTP) reacts with microgram amounts of cobalt(II) at pH 6.5-9.8 forming a green colour and with nickel(II) at pH 7.5-10 forming a brown colour. The complexes are extracted into organic solvents like chloroform, ketones and esters. The cobalt(II)-MBTP complex when extracted with ethyl acetate has an absorption maximum at 350 nm. The nickel(II)-MBTP complex is conveniently extracted with chloroform and shows an absorption maximum at 415 nm. Both methods are efficient and sensitive. Many common ions are tolerated well. When the amounts of metals are in the order of milligrams they are quantitatively precipitated. Based on these, spectrophotometric and gravimetric methods for the determination of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) have been developed.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric methods

Preparation of MBTP has been described earlier¹.

Reagent and solution

A 1% (W/V) aqueous solution of MBTP was used for spectrophotometric work.

Standard solutions of the metals were prepared by dissolving known weights of AnalaR cobalt ammonium sulphate and nickel ammonium sulphate in predetermined volumes of distilled water. Cobalt(II) solution was standardised gravimetrically by pyridine-thiocyanate method². Nickel(II) solution was standardised gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime².

All other reagents and chemicals used were of AnalaR quality.

Ethyl acetate and chloroform used for extraction were purified by recommended methods³.

Apparatus

A Beckman DU₂ spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements. A Toshniwal Type 242 pH meter was employed for pH measurements.

Procedure

Place an aliquot of metal (containing 0.6 to 6.0 ppm of cobalt(II); 0.3 to 5.0 ppm of nickel(II)) in a separatory funnel and add 8 ml of 0.2M disodium phosphate, 2 ml of 0.1M citric acid and 2 ml of 1% (W/V) aqueous

solution of MBTP. Shake gently for 1 min. Add about 3 ml of purified solvent (ethyl acetate in the case of cobalt(II) and chloroform for nickel(II)). Shake vigorously for 2 min. Allow layers to separate. Transfer the coloured solvent layer to a small beaker containing about 0.5 g of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Extract twice more with 2 ml portions of solvent and collect in the same beaker. Transfer the combined extract to a 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with the solvent. Measure the absorbance at the optimum wavelength against the reagent blank.

Discussion

Absorbance Spectra

The absorbance spectra of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are shown in Fig 1 and Fig 2. In the former case, absorbance of the complex with respect to the reagent blank gradually increases from 310 nm to 350 nm and then decreases, whereas that of the reagent blank continuously decreases from 310 nm to 400 nm. Hence, 350 nm was chosen as the optimum wavelength for spectrophotometric work. In the latter case, absorbance of the complex increases from 390 nm, passes through a maximum at 415 nm and then decreases, whereas that of the reagent blank decreases from 390 nm upto 425 nm and thereafter remains practically constant. Hence, 415 nm was chosen as the optimum wavelength for spectrophotometric work.

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra

- 1.1 ppm cobalt + reagent vs. ethyl acetate blank;
- 1.1 ppm cobalt + reagent vs. reagent blank;
- reagent blank vs. ethyl acetate

Fig. 2. Absorption Spectra

- 1.63 ppm nickel + reagent vs. chloroform blank ;
- 1.63 ppm nickel + reagent vs. reagent blank ;
- reagent blank vs. chloroform.

Effect of reagent

For maximum colour development 1.5 ml of 1% (W/V) aqueous solution of MBTP was required. Excess of reagent had no effect on the absorbance provided the measurements were made against the respective reagent blanks.

The colour was stable for 24 hours at room temperature. Change of temperature from 20 to 40°C had no effect on the colour system.

Effect of pH

The optimum pH ranges for the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) was 6.5 to 9.8 and nickel(II) was 7.5 to 10. pH was maintained in the appropriate ranges by using Mac Ilvine's buffer mixtures. For this stock solutions of 0.2 M disodium phosphate and 0.1 M citric acid were prepared. 0.1% toluene was added as preservative. 8 ml of disodium phosphate solution was mixed with 2 ml of citric acid. This buffer mixture had a pH of about 7. On adding the ligand solution, pH shifted to the range 8 to 9.

Optimum range, photometric error and sensitivity

In the case of cobalt(II), the colour system obeyed Beer's law from 0.5 ppm to 6.0 ppm of metal. The optimum concentration range, as determined by the method of Ringbom⁴, was from 0.6 ppm to 5.5 ppm. In this range, the percentage relative analytical error per one per cent absolute photometric error⁵ was 1.615. The photometric sensitivity of the method was 0.0028 $\mu\text{g Co cm}^{-2}$ at 350nm. In the case of nickel(II), Beer's law was followed from 0.3 ppm to 5.0 ppm of metal. The optimum concentration range according to the method of Ringbom was 0.4 ppm to 4.5 ppm. In this range percentage relative analytical error per one percent absolute photometric error was 1.167. The

photometric sensitivity of the method was 0.0032 $\mu\text{g Ni cm}^{-2}$ at 415 nm.

Precision and accuracy

Statistical studies were made to estimate precision. Ten independent determinations on solutions containing 1.1 μg of cobalt(II) ml^{-1} and 1.63 μg of nickel(II) ml^{-1} gave mean absorbance values of 0.390 and 0.508 and standard deviations of 0.002 and 0.004 absorbance units respectively. Similar statistical studies of ten independent determinations on reagent blank solutions in both cases gave mean absorbance values of 0.048 and 0.032 and standard deviations of 0.002 and 0.0016 respectively.

Composition of the complexes

The stoichiometric composition of the complexes was determined by Job's method of continuous variations⁶ and molar ratio method⁷. The results indicated the ratio of metal to reagent to be 1 : 2 in cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes.

Effect of diverse ions

Many common ions were tolerated well. Thus, in the above determinations Na^+ , K^+ , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , As^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{4+} , Ti^{4+} , carbonate, citrate, phosphate, nitrate, borate, oxalate, tartrate, acetate and chloride are tolerated in 1000 times excess. However, serious interferences were observed for W^{6+} , U^{6+} , Mo^{5+} , Re^{5+} , V^{5+} , Se^{4+} , Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} and Ag^+ .

Coordination chemistry of the complexes

The $\text{Co}(\text{MBTP})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{MBTP})_2$ complexes were isolated in the solid state. Elemental Analysis: (1) Found, 13.28% Co and 28.80% S; Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{OS}_2)_2$, 13.23% Co and 28.74% S. (2) Found 13.12% Ni and 28.70% S; Calc. for $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{OS}_2)_2$, 13.19% Ni and 28.76% S. The molecular weights of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes were determined in nitrobenzene cryoscopically. The values obtained (437.5 and 434.4 respectively) showed that the complexes were monomeric. Values for molar conductance obtained in nitrobenzene showed that they were non-electrolytes. Infrared spectral studies of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes showed that the C-S stretching frequency of the ligand at 1008 cm^{-1} was shifted to 995 cm^{-1} and 990 cm^{-1} and the C=O stretching frequency of the ligand at 1145 cm^{-1} was shifted to 1135 cm^{-1} (in both), suggesting the formation of a 6-membered ring structure as given below. Metal-sulphur stretching frequencies were also observed at 370 cm^{-1} and 390 cm^{-1} in the far-infrared spectra of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature using a Gouy type balance gave a value of 1.74 BM for cobalt(II)-MBTP and 0.5 BM for nickel(II)-MBTP complexes. The magnetic moment for cobalt(II) complex agrees with the value expected for a low-spin d^7 ion in square planar structure. However, the nickel(II) complex is found to have a small paramagnetic moment. A d^8 ion in a square planar environment should be actually diamagnetic. The small paramagnetism observed could be due to a second order Zeeman effect and might represent temperature independent of paramagnetism.^{8,9}

Gravimetric methods

MBTP reacts with cobalt(II) at pH 6.5–9.8 to form dark green and with nickel(II) at pH 7–10 forming brown complexes. The complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in dilute mineral acids and organic solvents like nitrobenzene, chloroform, isobutylmethylketone, alcohol and acetophenone. They are stable at room temperature for 24 hours. The complexes can be conveniently filtered at the pump using a sintered G4 crucible and dried at 105–110°C and weighed as $\text{CO}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{OS}_2)_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{OS}_2)_2$.

Apparatus, reagents and solutions

A Toshniwal Type T 242 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Standard solutions of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) were prepared as described under spectrophotometric work but using larger amounts of salts².

A 2% (W/V) aqueous solution of MBTP was used as the complexing agent and a 0.05% (W/V) aqueous solution of the same reagent was used for washing the precipitate. All other reagents used were of AnalaR quality.

Procedure

An aliquot of cobalt(II) solution or nickel(II) solution containing 20 to 40 mg of metal is placed in a 250 ml beaker containing 90 ml of distilled water. To this is added 5.0 gm. of AnalaR citric acid and stirred well. Then dilute ammonia solution is added until the pH of solution falls in the range 7–8, as indicated by the pH meter. On adding 2% (W/V) aqueous solution of MBTP to this, with constant stirring the dark green cobalt(II) complex or brown nickel(II) complex is precipitated. The contents of the beaker are maintained hot around 80°C for 2–3 min. and let stand for 1 hour for the precipitate to settle. The clear supernatant solution was tested for completion of precipitation by adding a few drops of the reagent through the inner sides of the beaker using a jet tube. If no further precipitation occurs, it is filtered through a sintered glass crucible of porosity 4 and the precipitate is washed three or four times with 5 ml portions of a 0.05% (W/V) aqueous solution of the reagent and then it is washed twice with 5 ml portions of distilled water containing a few drops of ammonia. The filtrate should be free of citric acid

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Cobalt(II) added mg	Cobalt(II) found mg	% error
10.64	10.62	-0.20
21.28	21.20	-0.38
25.54	25.60	+0.24
27.66	27.72	+0.22
31.92	32.02	+0.31
42.56	42.48	-0.19
53.20	53.32	+0.23
63.84	63.90	+0.09

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

Nickel(II) added mg	Nickel(II) found mg	% error
11.92	11.90	-0.17
14.30	14.28	-0.14
20.27	20.30	+0.15
23.84	23.86	+0.08
29.80	29.84	+0.13
35.76	35.80	+0.20
41.72	41.72	0.00
47.68	47.66	-0.04
53.64	53.66	+0.04

TABLE 3—FOREIGN IONS TOLERATED IN THE GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF COBALT

Ion	Amount of ion mg	Cobalt(II) added mg	Cobalt(II) found mg	% error
Na ⁺	100	21.28	21.32	+0.19
Ca ⁺⁺	100	21.28	21.30	+0.09
Ba ⁺⁺	100	21.28	21.28	0.00
Zn ⁺⁺	250	21.28	21.26	-0.09
Pb ⁺⁺	100	21.28	21.35	+0.33
Ce ⁺⁺	200	21.28	21.28	0.00
Mo ⁺⁺	10	21.28	21.32	+0.18
Oxalate	200	21.28	21.30	+0.09
Acetate	250	21.28	21.34	+0.27
Chloride	200	21.28	21.26	-0.09

TABLE 4—FOREIGN IONS TOLERATED IN THE GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF NICKEL

Ion	Amount of ion mg	Nickel(III) added mg	Nickel(II) found mg	% error
Na ⁺	100.00	23.84	23.88	+0.17
Mg ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.86	+0.08
Ca ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.88	+0.17
Ba ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.78	-0.25
Fe ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.80	-0.17
Pb ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.92	+0.34
La ⁺⁺	50.00	23.84	23.80	-0.17
Mo ⁺⁺	30.00	23.84	23.78	-0.25
Chloride	200.00	23.84	23.80	-0.17
Acetate	250.00	23.84	23.88	+0.17
Oxalate	200.00	23.84	23.82	-0.08

as indicated by the absence of a white precipitate on warming with CaCl_2 solution. The precipitate is dried at $105 - 110^\circ\text{C}$ to constant weight and weighed as $\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{OS}_2)_2$ or $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_5\text{OS}_2)_2$ as the case may be. The gravimetric factors for these are 0.1323 and 0.1318 respectively. Results (mean of analysis in duplicate) are shown in Tables 1 and 2. Tables 3 and 4 summarise the effect of foreign ions tolerated in the gravimetric analysis of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) respectively. Thermogravimetric analysis studies of these complexes showed that the Co-MBTP complex was stable upto 300°C and Ni-MBTP complex upto 260°C .

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